

Post-assembly modification of Pt(II) metallacages provides an open door to medicinal applications

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Summary

Here, we report a general workflow for the facile microwave-assisted synthesis of kinetically inert platinum(II)-MCgs and their post-assembly modification (PAM) via amide coupling and copper-catalyzed click chemistry. This approach enables the incorporation of diverse functional groups under mild conditions, including a fluorescent rhodamine label for optical imaging, an integrin-targeting cyclo(RGDFK) peptide, and a DOTA-derived chelator for complexation of radioactive isotopes, demonstrating the versatility and compatibility of the method with biologically relevant functionalities. Beyond synthetic flexibility, we demonstrate that these Pt(II) MCgs can encapsulate chemotherapeutic agents, facilitate cellular imaging, and modulate biological responses. Targeted cages enhanced the intracellular delivery and cytotoxicity of doxorubicin in integrin-expressing cancer cells, while DOTA-functionalized cages were successfully radiolabeled with gallium-68 and lutetium-177 with high radiochemical purity (RCP). Overall, our work expands the synthetic accessibility and functional scope of Pt(II)-MCgs, paving the way to their application in drug delivery, imaging, supramolecular radiotheranostics, and beyond.

Introduction

Metallacages (MCgs) are self-assembled supramolecular coordination complexes characterized by a three-dimensional (3D) structure outlining a well-defined cavity.¹⁻⁶ These cavities have been explored for their host-guest chemistry and as molecular reactors, leading to a growing field of applications in molecular recognition and sensing, separation,⁷ gas storage,⁸ and catalysis.⁹⁻¹² Recently, biomedical applications have also been on the rise,¹³⁻¹⁶ with MCgs employed to host,

protect, and deliver both therapeutic drugs and imaging agents^{15,17,18} or even to feature intrinsic imaging capabilities.^{19,20} In all these instances, the possibility of modifying the basic MCg structures to introduce diverse functionalities pre- or post-self-assembly is highly relevant. Introducing modifications to the cage structure has broadened the range of applications, not only by tuning fundamental aspects, such as solubility and stimulus-responsiveness, but also by enabling functionalization with catalytically active moieties, integration into hybrid materials, or the inclusion of targeting ligands for medical applications.^{23,24}

Pre-assembly functionalization (PAF) of MCgs is the most common strategy and leverages established methods to covalently modify the cage-building blocks with the desired functional units. However, this strategy is limited by the compatibility of the self-assembly process with the type of functionalization, which can interfere with the MCg formation through steric hindrance, charge repulsion, unselective metal coordination, or off-path reactivity. Post-assembly modification (PAM) avoids these issues by modifying fully formed cages.²⁵⁻²⁹ However, only a few MCg systems are robust enough to withstand the reaction conditions required for PAM without decomposing or undergoing side reactions.

Palladium(II) MCgs of the type Pd_nL_m (L = ligand bearing pyridines or other nitrogen heterocycles as donor groups) are among the most studied types of assemblies, and many conceptual studies have addressed them to demonstrate the ability of increasing the complexity and function of coordination-driven self-assembled systems.^{6,30,31} In these systems, the kinetically labile nature of Pd-N bonds enables self-correction and prompt progression to the thermodynamically more favored 3D assemblies. While this dynamism can be exploited for some applications, it often results in suboptimal performance in more complex media, where high concentrations of nucleophiles, acids, bases, or metal ions compromise cage integrity. Despite their drawbacks, pre-assembly functionalized Pd₂L₄ cages have demonstrated their suitability for applications; for example, by integrating catalysts within the MCg cavity,^{32,33} or generating stimuli-responsive³⁴ and hybrid polymeric materials.³⁵ Our group has investigated medicinal applications beyond drug delivery via the incorporation of various building blocks, including fluorescent tags,³⁶⁻³⁹ targeting peptides,^{23,24,40} and radioisotopes.^{41,42} As all these functionalities must be introduced via pre-assembly functionalization, we have recently encountered challenges in introducing more complex (bulky/multicharged) targeting units.^{41,43}

On the other hand, Pd(II)-MCgs offer few possibilities for PAM, as they are incompatible with the reaction conditions of classical functionalization strategies, such as click reactions or amide bond formation. Instead, PAM of Pd(II)-MCgs has been achieved using soft reactions, such as imine formation⁴⁴ or the anthracene-maleimide Diels-Alder cycloaddition,⁴⁵ which have a limited scope in biologically relevant applications, due to either the reversibility of the process in aqueous media or to the limited availability of reagents compatible with the reaction, respectively.

Recent studies have employed platinum(II) as a promising isostructural alternative to overcome the limitations of Pd(II)-based cages.^{38,46-48} In fact, Pt(II) MCgs demonstrate enhanced stability due to more kinetically inert metal-ligand bonds.³⁸ Nonetheless, the formation of PtCgs requires anhydrous conditions, elevated temperatures, and long reaction times. Recently, strategies to make Pt₂L₄ cages synthetically more accessible have been reported.⁴⁶ While non-functionalized PtCgs are relatively abundant, some have been proposed in medical applications.⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰ Instead, functionalized PtCgs are far less common. In one case, allowing their *in vivo* biodistribution to be assessed in the zebrafish model, or for the delivery of siRNAs.⁵² Despite the proven suitability of

PtCgs as multifunctional scaffolds, incorporating biofunctional modifications remains a major challenge. This is due to the limited scope of functional groups that can be included using pre-assembly functionalization, and the lack of strategies for widely applicable PAM. To date, some efforts have reported PAM via amine-maleic anhydride coupling,⁵³ metal coordination sphere modification, or imine condensation.⁴⁴ Still, the available methods either lack a broad scope or rely on reversible bonds, which are suboptimal for aqueous applications.

In response to these challenges, we develop here the PAM of PtCgs as a readily available strategy to include a broad range of functionalities via amide bond formation and click chemistry. To this end, the synthesis of Pt₂L₄ cages featuring (bio-)conjugating moieties (i.e azide or N-Hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) ester groups) was optimized via a microwave (MW)-assisted method. Following PtCg formation, the possibility of efficient PAM was demonstrated by introducing various functionalities. Specifically, given our interest in the medicinal application of these systems, we introduced a fluorescent rhodamine label for optical imaging, the cyclo(RGDfK) integrin-targeting peptide,⁵⁵ and a 2,2',2'',2'''-(1,4,7,10-Tetraazacyclododecane-1,4,7,10-tetrayl)tetraacetic acid (DOTA)-derived chelator for radiolabeling. These functional units not only enable the initial evaluation of the biomedical properties of the cages, but also show the compatibility of the developed method with a wide variety of functional groups and substituent properties. Overall, by using widely applicable reactions, with a broad scope of easily accessible reagents, the presented PAM approach opens the door to the next generation of supramolecular drugs and theranostic agents, as well as to a whole original class of functionalized MCgs and MCg-based hierarchical structures.

Results and Discussion

Rapid and efficient synthesis of Pt₂L₄ MCgs

The first synthesis of lantern-shaped Pt₂L₄ (L = 3,3''-di(pyridin-4-yl)-1,1':3',1''-terphenyl) cages used PtCl₂ as metal source, which reacted in DMSO with the ligands in the presence of AgNO₃.⁴⁷ However, the most extended precursors in later reports are tetrakis-acetonitrileplatinum(II) salts ([Pt(CH₃CN)₄]X₂ with X = TfO⁻ (trifluoromethyl sulfonate) or BF₄⁻ (tetrafluoroborate),^{38,56,57} Only a few other options have been used, including the *in situ* precipitation of chlorides from [PtCl₂(CH₃CN)₂] using silver salts,⁴⁸ or the alternative use of [Pt(EtCN)₄](OTf)₂.⁵⁶ All these approaches require air-free, anhydrous reaction conditions and long reaction times (>12 h). More recently, Preston and coworkers have achieved the synthesis of Pt(II) cages using a more stable reagent bearing an electron-poor pyridine ligand ([Pt(3ClPy)₄]X₂, 3ClPy = 3-chloropyridine) under solvothermal conditions in acetonitrile.⁴⁶

Based on these previous reports, we investigated different Pt(II) precursors bearing electron-poor pyridines (Figure 1a) for their cage-forming ability with a model ligand (L^{CO^{OBn}}, benzyl 2-(3,5-bis(pyridin-3-ylethynyl)phenyl)acetate, Figure 1b, Scheme S1) using acetonitrile, methanol, and nitromethane as solvents (no Schlenk conditions were applied). The results and detailed conditions are summarized in Table 1. In all cases, we implemented microwave heating, following our previous results in synthesizing other families of MCgs using this technique⁵⁸, which allowed for shorter reaction times. In our conditions, the recently reported [Pt(3ClPy)₄](OTf)₂⁴⁶ led to a high yield of cage formation in acetonitrile (Figure S1a). However, although some conversion was achieved in methanol and nitromethane, several peaks in the NMR region of the pyridine's hydrogen nuclei vicinal to the coordinating nitrogen atom on the PtCg (δ = 9.0-10.0 ppm, Figure S1a) indicate that several species could be formed. We next evaluated a different precursor, [Pt(4CF₃Py)₄](NO₃)₂ (4CF₃Py = 4-trifluoromethylpyridine), compared to the previous example; this compound bears the strongest CF₃ electron-withdrawing group, which would be expected to favour ligand-exchange reactions. Interestingly, this precursor enabled cage formation in

methanol, whereas conversion was incomplete in acetonitrile (Figure S1b). No cage formation was observed in nitromethane. Our efforts for further decreasing the electron-donor capabilities of the precursor's ligand, adding a fluorine atom in the pyridine ring, were not successful, as the reagent $[\text{Pt}(\text{2F4CF}_3\text{Py})_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$ ($\text{2F4CF}_3\text{Py}$ = 2-fluoro-4-trifluoromethylpyridine) could not be prepared due to the serendipitous activation of the C-F bond by Pt(II), generating instead the compound $[\text{Pt}(\text{2OMe4CF}_3\text{Py})_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$ ($\text{2OMe4CF}_3\text{Py}$ = 2-methoxy-4-trifluoromethylpyridine). The latter showed the poorest conversion, consistent with the presence of the electron-donating methoxy group, and produced only coordination species with methanol as a solvent and in lower yield than the 3-chloropyridine precursor (Figure S1c).

While the studied pyridylplatinum(II) precursors are stable and require no inert conditions for the reaction, the presence of the pyridine ligands as byproducts in solution demands an additional purification step, which is not needed in the case of $[\text{Pt}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4]^{2+}$. In our quest for the most convenient conditions for cage formation, we also used $[\text{Pt}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2(\text{PhCN})_2]\text{OTf}$, yielding similar results and requiring the same inert reaction conditions as the acetonitrile precursor (data not shown). Besides these multiple options, we found that the one-pot synthesis using $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_2]$, a common air and water-stable platinum precursor, in the presence of AgOTf was straightforward in acetonitrile and methanol, giving good yields, with no evidence of disturbance of the self-assembly process by the presence of Ag^+ ions (Figure S1d). However, different species formed in nitromethane using this approach; in general, this solvent yielded the poorest results, regardless of the precursor used.

Table 1 | Pt_2L_4 cage formation reaction yields with different solvents and variation of the Pt(II) precursor. Cage formation was conducted with L^{COOBn} (1.00 equiv.) and Pt(II)-Precursor (0.60 equiv.) in 1.5 mL of deuterated solvent in the microwave at 150 °C for 1.5 hours. The conversion is calculated from the relative NMR integration of the pyridyl signals of Pt(II)-coordinated and free L^{COOBn} .

Solvent	Pt-Precursor			
	$[\text{Pt}(\text{3ClPy})_4](\text{OTf})_2^{46}$	$[\text{Pt}(\text{4CF}_3\text{Py})_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$	$[\text{Pt}(\text{2OMe4CF}_3\text{Py})_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$	$[\text{Pt}(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2] + 2\text{AgOTf}$
MeCN	87%	66%	0%	96%
MeOH	63%	92%	45%	82%
MeNO ₂	19%	2%	0%	34%

Figure 1 | Metallacage synthesis and characterization. (a) Chemical structures of investigated Pt(II)-precursors (b) Coordination-driven self-assembly of PtCgs, the various Pt(II) precursors, solvents and yields are shown in Table 1. (c) HR-ESI-MS of PtCg; the inset shows the detail of the isotopic pattern of the species $[Pt_2L^{COOBn}_4]^{4+}$ (m/z 525.8841, $\Delta_{\text{exp-calc}} = 1.5$ ppm). (d) Partial ^1H -NMR spectra of free ligand L^{COOBn} , the cage $Pt_2L^{COOBn}_4$, and ^1H -DOSY NMR spectrum of $Pt_2L^{COOBn}_4$ in CD_3CN at 25°C , showing the characteristic downfield shift of the pyridine protons upon cage formation (full spectra available in Figure S2).

The formed $Pt_2L^{COOBn}_4$ metallacage was characterized by various methods, including high-resolution electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (HR-ESI-MS), 1D (^1H and ^{13}C) NMR spectroscopy, and ^1H diffusion-ordered spectroscopy (DOSY) (Figure S2). HR-ESI-MS spectra revealed different charged species, whose isotopic patterns confirmed the identity of the desired PtCg (Figure 1c). Evaluation of the ^1H -NMR spectrum of the PtCg and comparison to the free ligand showed a deprotection of the pyridine protons, indicating cage formation. This effect results from the high positive charge density at the Pt(II) centers in the PtCg. Moreover, the single-component nature of the metallacage was confirmed using ^1H DOSY NMR spectroscopy (Figure 1d). A single diffusion coefficient of $5.5 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ was deduced, which accounts for a hydrodynamic radius of about 1.3 nm – according to the Stokes-Einstein-Gierer-Wirtz approximation implemented in the program SEGWE.⁵⁹ Single crystals of $Pt_2L^{COOBn}_4$ were obtained by slow diffusion of diethyl ether in a solution of the cage into THF. The single-crystal X-ray (SCXR) analysis confirmed the expected cage structure, where each Pt(II) ion is coordinated to four pyridyl donors in a square-planar geometry (Figure 2). In the crystal, the lantern-shaped cages' internal cavity was occupied by one highly disordered triflate anion (Figure S3, Data S1-S2), while

the remaining ones are positioned in the close surroundings of the PtCg, interacting in the packing with neighboring cage units.

Figure 2 | XRD structural analysis. ORTEP representations of the SCXRD structure of $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{COOBn}}_4$ (CCDC 2515887) shown with 40 % probability displacement ellipsoids; (a) overall cage structure, (b) side and (c) top-down views. Hydrogen atoms and triflate counterions are omitted for clarity. The colour code is as follows C = gray, N = blue, O = red, and Pt = teal. The structures were generated using Mercury.⁶⁰

The stability of PtCg was assessed in different media; specifically, $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{COOBn}}_4$ (4 μM) was solubilized in MilliQ H_2O , PBS (pH 7.4), DIPEA (pH 10), and HCl (2M), and its UV-Vis absorption spectrum was monitored over 24 h (Figure S4). For all four conditions, the spectral profile remained largely unchanged, except for slight intensity variations related to precipitation, indicating good stability over the measured time frame. Next, the stability towards the model nucleophile N-Acetyl-Cysteine (20 equiv.) and DIPEA (20 equiv.) was evaluated by ^1H NMR spectroscopy. A comparison between the cage and free ligand signals showed 88% intact PtCg after 24 h in the presence of N-Acetyl-Cysteine (Figure S5), and no decomposition was observed in the presence of DIPEA (Figure S6). Overall, these experiments show the higher stability of PtCgs when compared to similar Pd-based cages in similar conditions (Table S3).

Post-Assembly exo-functionalized MCgs by amide bond formation and alkyne-azido click chemistry

Amide coupling and azido-alkyne cycloaddition click reactions are among the most widely applicable strategies for integrating functionalities across the broad chemical context. Thus, we aimed to construct Pt_2L_4 platforms with groups capable of participating in these reactions, thereby granting a wide scope of functionalities that can be integrated efficiently (Figure 3a). To achieve PAM via amide coupling, we first attempted the cage synthesis using a carboxylic acid-containing ligand (L^{COOH} , 2-(3,5-bis(pyridin-3-ylethynyl)phenyl)acetic acid). However, no cage was formed, probably due to the formation of charge separation adducts⁶¹ between the carboxylic acid of the ligand and the platinum(II) source. Having in hand the benzyl-protected cage, $[\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{COOBn}}_4](\text{TfO})_4$, we attempted its deprotection, which was unsuccessful, as the addition of NaOH (4.00 equiv.) led to complete decomposition, possibly through the formation of insoluble hydroxides under these harsh conditions. Milder basic conditions were also attempted, but they did not enable deprotection. A convenient alternative was identified using an NHS-ester

containing ligand (L^{NHS} , 2,5-dioxopyrrolidin-1-yl 2-(3,5-bis(pyridin-3-ylethynyl)phenyl)acetate, Figure 3b), which allowed the quantitative formation of the activated $[Pt_2L^{NHS}_4](TfO)_4$ cage, as confirmed by NMR spectroscopy and HR-ESI-MS (Figures S7-S8). $Pt_2L^{NHS}_4$ was further used without purification to integrate diverse groups via the reaction with primary amine derivatives. In this way, PtCgs *exo*-functionalized with a peptide (*cyclo*(RGDfK)) for $\alpha v\beta 3$ integrin targeting,⁶² Rhodamine B as fluorescence imaging label, and a DOTA chelator for radiolabeling ($Pt_2L^{RGD}_4$, $Pt_2L^{Rho}_4$, and $Pt_2L^{DOTA}_4$, Figure 3c) were obtained by PAM, yielding mainly completely substituted MCgs which were purified via HPLC (high-pressure liquid chromatography, Figure S9) as confirmed by HR-ESI-MS (Figure 3d). Overall, our PAM strategy proved successful for a range of reagents useful in medicinal applications, and it could also be extended to virtually any other kind of substitution.

Figure 3 | PAM of Pt(II) cages via amide coupling and characterization. (a) Schematic representation of PAM of Pt_2L_4 cages with functional groups. (b) NHS-ester strategy for post-functionalization via amide coupling. (c) cyclo(RGDFK)-peptide, rhodamine B derivative, or DOTA-derivative attached to the Pt(II) cages via PAM. (d) HR-ESI-MS of PtCgs obtained for $Pt_2L_4^{RGD}_4$ (top), $Pt_2L_4^{Rho}_4$ (middle) and $Pt_2L_4^{DOTA}_4$ (bottom). The insets show the detail of the isotopic pattern of the species $[Pt_2L_4^{RGD}_4]^{4+}$ (m/z 1021.3899, $\Delta_{exp-calc}$ = 0.9 ppm), $[Pt_2L_4^{Rho}_4]^{5+}$ (m/z 500.3351, $\Delta_{exp-calc}$ = 4.2 ppm), and $[Pt_2L_4^{DOTA}_4]^{4+}$ (m/z 920.3896, $\Delta_{exp-calc}$ = 0.1 ppm).

To use click chemistry as a post-functionalization strategy, we synthesized an azide-bearing cage ($\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Azide}}_4$, Figure 4a). Including the azide group enables functionalization via the copper-catalyzed click reaction with a wide range of alkyne reagents and strain-promoted copper-free reagents, both of great relevance in biorthogonal chemistry. In the case of the copper-catalyzed reaction, $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Azide}}_4$ demonstrated the capability of standing the standard click reaction conditions, and neither the addition of Cu^{2+} ions nor alkyne-based ligands compromised its stability. Importantly, the formation of the PAM products was assessed using an alkyne-functionalized rhodamine derivative (Figure 4a). However, despite our attempts to achieve complete functionalization — by increasing reaction times, catalyst and reagent amounts — we have consistently observed mixtures by HR-ESI-MS. Along with the fully substituted product, partially substituted adducts containing all possible combinations of one to three modified side-chains were detected (Figure 4b). A similar result was observed for strain-promoted click PAM with an amine-containing dibenzocyclooctyne (DBCO; Figure 4c). In this case, the reaction yielded a mixture containing partially functionalized cages with one to three modified side-chains in the *exo*-position. Of note, in this reaction mixture, the L^{Azide} ligands in the cage structure fragmented during the MS process, losing the terminal fragment of the azide-bearing PEG ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_3$, Figure S10). Although click-based PAM requires further optimization, including a detailed study of possible off-pathways hindering the full conversion in this type of system, we have demonstrated the feasibility of utilizing both Cu-catalyzed and strain-promoted click chemistry on azide-containing Pt(II) MCgs for PAM.

Figure 4 | PAM of Pt(II) cages via 'click' chemistry and characterization. (a) Click-reaction strategy for post-functionalization via a copper-catalyzed or strain-promoted approach. (b) HR-ESI-MS of $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Click}}_4$; the inset shows the detail of the isotopic pattern of the species $[\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Click}}_4]^{4+}$ (m/z 1115.4755, $\Delta_{\text{exp-calc}} = 1.4$ ppm), other observed ions are indicated within the spectrum. (c) HR-ESI-MS of $\text{PtCgPt}_2\text{L}^{\text{DBCO}}_4$; the inset shows the detail of the isotopic pattern of the species $[\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Azide}}_2\text{L}^{\text{DBCO}}_2]^{2+}$ (m/z 599.2106, $\Delta_{\text{exp-calc}} = 6.7$ ppm), other observed ions are indicated within the spectrum.

Furthermore, we decided to explore tandem functionalization, which could reduce the number of purification steps and enable the subsequent addition of differently functionalized building blocks, thereby increasing the complexity of the systems and the efficiency of their production. Improving the scalability and adaptability of the synthesis of complex cage-based platforms is crucial to render them compatible with continuous flow and automated synthetic

strategies in industrial settings. Therefore, we envisaged a tandem one-pot reaction depicted in Figure 5a-b. Starting from the $[\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{NHS}}_4](\text{TfO})_4$ cage, an azide-containing tetraethylene glycol amine linker was integrated through amide coupling, giving $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Azide}}_4$ (Figure 5c). Upon reaction completion (as assessed by HR-ESI-MS and NMR spectroscopy), the reagents for the click reaction were added to the crude reaction mixture, allowing the *in situ* formation of the rhodamine-substituted cage ($\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Click}}_4$). As in the direct click reaction, the full integration of the rhodamine moiety was not complete after the click step (Figure 5d). Despite this limitation, the example demonstrated a viable approach to executing multiple steps of cage functionalization within a tandem reaction framework.

Figure 5 | PAM of Pt(II) cages via tandem coupling and characterization. (a) Schematic representation of tandem PAM via amide coupling reaction and subsequent copper-catalysed click reaction. (b) Tandem strategy for post-functionalization via amide coupling with PEG-linker (in dry acetonitrile at RT) followed by copper-catalysed click reaction with a Rhodamine B derivative (in acetonitrile/H₂O 2:1 at RT). (c) HR-ESI-MS of $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Azide}}_4$; the inset shows the detail of the isotopic pattern of the species $[\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Azide}}_4]^{4+}$ (m/z 635.9649, $\Delta_{\text{exp-calc}} = 0.2$ ppm). (d) HR-ESI-MS of $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Click}}_4$; the inset shows the detail of the isotopic pattern of the species $[\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Click}}_4]^{4+}$ (m/z 1115.4726, $\Delta_{\text{exp-calc}} = 1.3$ ppm). The spectrum shows the presence of partially exo-functionalized cages, together with the homoleptic $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Click}}_4$; the identity of the major peaks is indicated in the figure.

Doxorubicin encapsulation

The most prominent feature of metallacages in medical applications is their ability to act as hosts for encapsulating and transporting molecular cargoes.^{56,63,64} M_2L_4 metallacages can efficiently

host quinones and related 1,4-dicarbonyl-containing moieties via matching H-bonding between the oxygens and the pyridine endohedral hydrogens.⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶ Recently, the encapsulation of the chemotherapeutic drug Doxorubicin (Doxo) has also been reported in a Pd₂L₄ cage with an estimated association constant in the range of 10⁴ M⁻¹.⁶⁷ However, the used Pd cage degraded in the presence of the drug, making it difficult to reproduce the binding experiment. Motivated by the higher stability of PtCgs, we evaluated their capabilities to encapsulate Doxo. An initial computational assessment of Doxo's fit within the cavity of Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ was performed (see SI for computational details).^{68,69} The Non-Covalent Interactions (NCI) analysis⁷⁰ of the optimized host-guest complex (Figure 6a) shows attractive regions (blue/green surfaces) corresponding to a combination of polar H-bonding contacts between the endohedral α-pyridyl protons and the anthracycline oxygens of Doxo, together with apolar dispersive contacts among the cage's and host's aromatic backbones; the more voluminous daunosamine group is positioned in one of the cage's windows. This mode of binding was supported by ¹H NMR (Figure S11a), in a mixture in MeCN-d₃/DMSO-d₆ (3:1), by a clear deshielding of the signal assigned to endohedral α-pyridyl protons ($\Delta\delta \approx 0.6$ ppm) together with a small shielding of the central phenyl ring endohedral proton ($\Delta\delta \approx 0.1$ ppm). Interestingly, upon addition of an excess of guest, the exohedral α-pyridyl protons also deshield, suggesting the possibility of exohedral secondary binding of Doxo to Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄. Under these conditions, the Doxo<PtCg adduct (1:1) showed no signs of degradation after 24 hours (Figure S11b). Although NMR experiments in aqueous conditions are precluded by the low solubility of both host and guest, the experimental binding constant of Doxo to Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ in PBS (140 mM NaCl, 10 mM phosphate buffer, 3 mM KCl, pH 7.4) was obtained via fluorometric titration, taking advantage of the quenching of the emission of Doxo ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 596$ nm) upon binding to the PtCg. The fitting of the data yielded a considerable apparent association constant, $K_a = 6.4 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($\pm 2.3\%$; Figure 6b), which is in the same order of magnitude as the reported association constant to the Pd cage and accounts for the displacement of anions that likely occupy the cavity in solution, indicating a greater affinity of the cage for Doxo.

Figure 6 | Encapsulation of doxorubicin in PtCgs. (a) NCI analysis of the optimized Doxo-cPtCg complex. NCI plots visualize non-covalent interactions via isosurfaces of the second eigenvalue of the electron density Hessian ($\lambda_2\rho$), where blue/green regions ($\lambda_2\rho < 0$) indicate attractive H-bonds/dispersion and red ($\lambda_2\rho > 0$) shows steric repulsion. The colour code is as follows C = gray, N = blue, O = red, and Pt = teal, the visualization was generated using VMD.⁷¹ (b) Fluorometric titrations of doxorubicin (20 μM Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ in PBS pH 7.4, 1% DMSO). [G]/[H] refers to the molar ratio of the guest (G, Doxo) to the host (H, Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄). (c) Fluorometric titrations of Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ to BSA (0.5 μM BSA in phosphate buffer, pH 7.4, 1.5% CH₃CN). In this case, BSA was considered the host.

Serum albumin binding studies

Albumin is a plasma protein existing in all mammals in high concentrations (60% of all plasma proteins). Its primary function is the transportation of apolar and positively charged molecules within the body. Recently, Pt(II) metallacages functionalized with rhodamine have been shown to bind bovine albumin (BSA).³⁸ Herein, we investigated the binding of the simpler Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ cage to BSA. We performed a fluorometric titration experiment by the addition of Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ to a BSA solution in phosphate buffer pH = 7.2 (see Supplemental Methods for details) (Figure 6b). Analysis of the quenching of the emission spectra of the BSA tryptophan residues upon binding of the cage ($\lambda_{\text{em}} = 350$ nm, Figure 6c) suggested the formation of a 2:1 complex with high binding constants $K_{11} = 8.3 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($\pm 5.6\%$) and $K_{12} = 1.1 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($\pm 2.0\%$); K_{11} is the association constant for the formation of a 1:1 complex while K_{12} refers to the association constant for the second binding step. These results indicate that the cage can bind to the two available hydrophobic binding pockets of the protein, and given the close values, the binding selectivity is limited. Although fluorometric titration relies on the assumption of dominant static quenching mechanisms, and although the optical density was below 0.1 in these experiments, some error is possible. However, slightly different rhodamine-functionalized cages have shown cumulative binding constants within the 10⁶–10⁷ range, as determined by Isothermal Titration Calorimetry.³⁸ The higher cumulative binding affinity of Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ for BSA is consistent with the higher hydrophobicity expected for this system compared to the functionalized ones. The high binding

constants, both for the functionalized and unfunctionalized systems, support that albumin interaction may play a significant role in the biodistribution of MCgs and potentially influence their activity *in vivo*.³⁸ The available studies of the interaction of PtCgs with serum proteins are limited, and further investigations are needed to clarify the structural nature of the interactions suggested for the spectroscopic and calorimetric methods.

Antiproliferative Activity, cellular uptake and drug delivery

In order to assess the biocompatibility of the Pt cages, the antiproliferative effects of the unfunctionalized $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{COOBn}}_4$ and its ligand L^{COOBn} were tested in human cancer cell lines A549 (lung carcinoma) and A375 (melanoma), and the human non-cancer cell line Hek293, using the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay. The EC_{50} (effective concentration to reduce cell viability to 50%) values are reported in Figure 7a (Figure S12-S13 and Table S6). While the free ligand L^{COOBn} shows medium to low cytotoxicity in the tested cell lines in comparison to cisplatin over 72 h, cage $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{COOBn}}_4$ shows no cytotoxicity at the maximal tested concentration (100 μM). Preliminary data also confirmed that the rhodamine-*exo*-functionalized cage ($\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Rho}}_4$, Figure 3c) is non-toxic at 10 μM concentration over a 24-hour incubation period (data not shown). Thus, we assessed their cellular uptake and subcellular distribution in A549 cells. Fluorescence emission studies revealed that $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Rho}}_4$ retains the characteristic emission and absorption wavelengths of Rhodamine B in water, albeit with a 10-fold reduction in its photoluminescent quantum yield (PLQY, Table 2 and Figure S14). This is likely due to the activation of non-radiative relaxation pathways via the heavy-atom effect.^{72,73} Nevertheless, the intensity of this emission was suitable for detection via fluorescence confocal microscopy.

Table 2 | Photophysical characterization. Absorption, Emission and photoluminescent quantum yield (PLQY) of $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Rho}}_4$ (10 μM), L^{Rho} (10 μM), and Rhodamine B (0.5 μM) in water.

Compound	Absorption λ_{max} (nm)	Emission λ_{max} (nm)	PLQY
$\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Rho}}_4$	557	579	0.033
L^{Rho}	557	576	0.102
Rhodamine B	554	576	0.303

Therefore, the uptake and subcellular localization of the $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Rho}}_4$ cage were studied by confocal fluorescence microscopy in comparison to the ligand L^{Rho} . After 2 hours and 24 hours incubation, A549 cells were fixed, and nuclear (Hoechst 33342) and plasma membrane (CellMask™ Deep Red) staining was performed. The results obtained showed that the cage and its ligand were well internalized within the first 2 hours and exhibited a similar subcellular distribution (Figure 7b-c). The larger fluorescence signal detected for L^{Rho} may be attributed to its higher PLQY rather than to better uptake. Moreover, $\text{Pt}_2\text{L}^{\text{Rho}}_4$ and L^{Rho} did not reach the nuclei, but were distributed in the cytoplasm as confirmed by the z-stack view (Figure 7c).

Figure 7 | Cell viability assays in human cancer cells. (a) Antiproliferative activity (EC₅₀) of Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ determined in cancer A375 (melanoma), A549 (lung adenocarcinoma), and non-tumorigenic HEK293 (embryonic kidney) cells after 72 h. **(b)** Confocal fluorescence microscopy images showing the comparative internalization of L^{Rho} and Pt₂L^{Rho}₄ at 2 h and 24 h after treatment in A549 cells. **(c)** Z-stack showing the intracellular localization of Pt₂L^{Rho}₄ (pink), the scale bar is 20 μm. In the confocal images, staining of the nucleus (Hoechst 33342) in blue, plasma membrane (Cell Mask™ deep red) in cyan, and rhodamine moiety in pink.

In the next step, the targeting abilities of Pt₂L^{RGD}₄ were evaluated in A375 cells, which are characterized by αvβ3 integrin-receptor overexpression,⁷⁴ and compared with the effects recorded on A549 cells, featuring no expression of the αvβ3 integrin-receptor.⁷⁵ The expression profile of integrins in Hek293 cells remains controversial. While some studies report that Hek293 cells do not express the αvβ3 and αvβ5 integrins,^{76,77} other studies have documented their presence in the same cell line.⁷⁸ In contrast, HEK293 cells have consistently been shown to express α5β1 and αvβ1 integrins, which are RGD-dependent receptors for the extracellular matrix glycoproteins fibronectin and vitronectin.⁷⁹

A comparative cell viability assay was conducted in which the three distinct cell lines were exposed to the integrin-targeted cage encapsulating Doxo (Doxo<Pt₂L^{RGD}₄) for 24 and 72 hours (Figures 8a and S16a, Table S5). The results were compared to those obtained for the treatments with free Doxorubicin (Table S6 and Figure S15) and the empty Pt₂L^{RGD}₄. Fixed concentrations per treatment were selected to correspond to the EC₅₀ values obtained for doxorubicin (0.93 μM for A375, 3.12 μM for A549, and 5.58 μM for Hek293 cells). When administered alone, Pt₂L^{RGD}₄ exhibited negligible to minimal cytotoxicity across the tested concentrations in both A375 and A549 cells (Figure 8a). In contrast, Doxo<Pt₂L^{RGD}₄ demonstrates significantly enhanced cytotoxicity (cell viability = 14.5 ± 4.5 % at [Doxo<Pt₂L^{RGD}₄] = 0.93 μM, at 24 h) compared to free doxorubicin in A375 cells (cell viability = 44.4 ± 8.1 % at [Doxo] = 0.93 μM), which are characterized by elevated αvβ3 integrin expression. In the non-αvβ3-expressing A549 cells, the antiproliferative activity of Doxo<Pt₂L^{RGD}₄ was in the same range as the one observed with free Doxo. Notably, Pt₂L^{RGD}₄ alone exhibits strong cytotoxicity against Hek293 cells. However, the underlying mechanism remains unclear and cannot be conclusively attributed to a specific integrin-

mediated pathway at this stage, particularly given the variability reported in integrin expression profiles for HEK293 cells.

To further test the targeting and encapsulation abilities of $Pt_2L^{RGD}_4$, fluorescence confocal microscopy was performed in A375 and A549 cells, exploiting the fluorescent properties of Doxo (Table S7). Distinct patterns of intracellular localization were observed across the tested cell lines. In A375 cells, free Doxo was predominantly internalized and accumulated within the nucleus, consistent with its mode of action as a DNA-intercalating agent (Figure 8b and d).⁸⁰ In addition to the nucleus, when Doxo \llcorner $Pt_2L^{RGD}_4$ was administered, association with the plasma membrane was evident (Figure 8b-d), suggesting an altered uptake mechanism potentially mediated by integrin interactions with the cage structure. When compared to A549 cells, both free Doxorubicin and Doxo \llcorner $Pt_2L^{RGD}_4$ displayed similar nuclear localization, indicating that in this cell line the encapsulation did not alter the intracellular distribution of the drug (Figure S16b-c). These findings are in line with the antiproliferative activity data, suggesting that the cellular uptake and subcellular distribution of Doxo \llcorner $Pt_2L^{RGD}_4$ are strongly influenced by integrin expression levels, with Doxo \llcorner $Pt_2L^{RGD}_4$ demonstrating targeted membrane interactions in integrin-overexpressing A375 cells, while maintaining conventional nuclear accumulation in A549 cells.

Figure 8 | Cell viability assays and internalization of the host-guest complex in human cancer cells. (a) Antiproliferative activity (EC_{50}) of Doxo@ $Pt_2L^{RGD_4}$ compared to free $Pt_2L^{RGD_4}$ and Doxorubicin in human cancer A375 (melanoma), A549 (lung adenocarcinoma), and non-tumorigenic HEK293 (embryonic kidney) cells after 24 h. Treatment concentrations are 0.93 μ M for A375, 3.12 μ M for A549, and 5.58 μ M for Hek293 cells. (b) Confocal fluorescence microscopy images showing the comparative internalization of Doxorubicin (Doxo) and Doxo@ $Pt_2L^{RGD_4}$ in A375 cells at 2 h and 24 h after treatment. (c) Z-stack showing the intracellular localization of Doxo@ $Pt_2L^{RGD_4}$ in A375-cells at 24 h. (d) Confocal fluorescence microscopy images showing the comparative internalization of Doxorubicin (Doxo) and Doxo@ $Pt_2L^{RGD_4}$ in A375 cells at 24 h after treatment in a closer frame. In the confocal images, staining of the nucleus (Hoechst 33342) in blue, plasma membrane (Cell Mask™ deep red) in cyan, and Doxorubicin (free or encapsulated) in red.

Having established how ligand functionalization and encapsulation influence cellular uptake and biological behavior, we next explored how this design principles translate to the development of Pt(II) cages for nuclear imaging and therapeutic applications. To this aim, the DOTA-functionalized Pt(II) cage ($Pt_2L^{DOTA_4}$) was successfully radiolabeled with gallium-68 (Figure 9a). Radiolabeling conditions were systematically evaluated by varying the amount of $Pt_2L^{DOTA_4}$ precursor (Table S8), revealing that higher precursor concentrations led to higher radiochemical purity (RCP). Under optimized conditions, radiolabeling with 50 MBq of gallium-68 afforded a RCP of 92.68% (Figure 9b). Furthermore, $Pt_2L^{DOTA_4}$ demonstrated excellent radiolabeling efficiency with lutetium-177 (RCP 96.02%) (Figure 9c). Collectively, these results confirm that the DOTA-

functionalized Pt(II) cage provides a robust and versatile platform for radiolabeling, underscoring its suitability for dual-modality nuclear imaging and therapeutic applications. Further work will be devoted to integrating targeting peptides into the cage *exo*-functionalization, together with DOTA chelators, to overcome the limitations observed for Pd(II) cages and to allow the development of a new generation of supramolecular radiopharmaceuticals.⁸¹

Figure 9 | Radiolabeling of PtCgs and Radio-HPLC characterization. (a) Schematic representation for radiolabeling of Pt₂L₄DOTA₄ using a radionuclide. (b) ⁶⁸Ga Radio-HPLC chromatograms of radiolabeled Pt₂L₄DOTA₄ (50 µg) using ⁶⁸Ga (50 MBq). (c) ¹⁷⁷Lu Radio-HPLC chromatograms of radiolabeled Pt₂L₄DOTA₄ (50 µg) using ¹⁷⁷Lu (8.7 MBq).

In conclusion, this work provides a robust methodology for facile, versatile synthesis and broadly applicable functionalization of Pt₂L₄ MCgs. The generated strategies enable the synthesis of Pt-based cages using air-stable, commercially available Pt(II) precursors in shorter times and with efficiencies similar to those of previously reported methods that require inert synthetic conditions. Furthermore, the practical and straightforward post-assembly modification of such MCgs via amide bond formation and click chemistry was demonstrated, not only unlocking access to otherwise challenging functionalization relevant for biomedical applications, such as fluorescent tags, targeting groups, and chelating agents, but also enabling the generation of a broad range of functional systems for all types of purposes. Beyond their streamlined synthesis and modularity, we show that these cages can encapsulate chemotherapeutic agents, preserve their structural integrity under biological conditions, and enable controlled drug delivery. Encapsulated Doxo retained - or, when combined with targeting units, even enhanced - its cytotoxic activity in cancer cell lines, highlighting the potential of host-guest chemistry-based *Trojan horse* approaches⁸² to improve drug delivery. Fluorescence imaging experiments further validated efficient cellular uptake and demonstrated that targeted PtCgs feature specific localization profiles compared to their non-functionalized counterparts. Importantly for nuclear medicine applications, the DOTA-functionalized PtCg was successfully radiolabeled with both gallium-68 and lutetium-177, achieving high radiochemical purity. Collectively, these findings

expand the application of metallacages as next-generation biomedical tools for the development of drug-delivery systems, multifunctional drugs, and theranostic platforms. Specifically, our focus will be on the development of supramolecular radiopharmaceuticals targeted to brain cancer. Beyond medicinal applications, this work contributes to a general framework for functionalizing MCgs post-assembly, laying the groundwork for transformative developments in other emerging areas, such as sensing and catalysis.

Methods

Biological Assays

Cell Maintenance: Melanoma cancer cells (A375), human embryonic kidney cells (Hek293), and lung cancer cells (A549) were maintained in Dulbecco's modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, GIBCO), supplemented with 10 % (v/v) inactivated foetal calf serum (FCS, GIBCO), L-glutamine solution 200 nm (1% v/v, 2 nm end concentration), and 0.05 mg/ml Gentamicin (GIBCO). Cells were incubated under controlled conditions of 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Cells were passaged every 72 hours using 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA (1x) after washing with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS; pH 7.4). A549 and Hek293 cells were from the DSMZ Helmholtz Institute for Infection Research (HZI, Braunschweig, Germany), while A375 cells were from Cyton/Cell Line Service. Ultrapure water (18.2 MΩ/0.56 μS at 25 °C) was provided by a BerryPure® mini from Berrytec. All reagents were purchased from Gibco™ (Thermo Scientific), and solvents from Sigma-Aldrich.

Antiproliferative activity assays: HEK 293 cells, A549 cells, and A375 cells were seeded in 96-well culture plates and incubated in a 5% CO₂ incubator at 37°C for 24 hours before being treated with different concentrations of the selected compound (0.04-100 μM) (Table S4). Stock solutions of L^{COOBn}₄ and Pt₂L^{COOBn}₄ (20 mM) were prepared in DMSO and diluted with DMEM to 100 μM and 75 μM prior to cell treatment. Stock solutions of cisplatin (Sigma-Aldrich) were prepared in MilliQ water. Stock solutions of doxorubicin, and Pt₂L^{RGD}₄, (10 mM) were prepared in MilliQ water. A Stock solution of Doxo-Pt₂L^{RGD}₄ (10 mM) was prepared by mixing Pt₂L^{RGD}₄ (1 equiv.) and Doxorubicin (1 equiv.) in MilliQ water. The obtained stock solutions of doxorubicin, cisplatin Pt₂L^{RGD}₄, and Doxo-Pt₂L^{RGD}₄ were diluted in DMEM to 20 μM, 5.58 μM, 3.12 μM, and 0.93 μM prior to cell treatment (Table S5).

After either 24 hours or 72 hours of incubation, cell survival was assessed by colorimetric 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT, Sigma Aldrich) staining. Thus, the media was removed from the wells, and 100 μL of media containing MTT solution (8 mg in 1.6 mL of PBS, sterile-filtered into 14.4 mL DMEM) was added to each well of a 96-well plate, which was then incubated for 2 hours at 37 °C. Viable cells convert the yellow-coloured MTT into dark-blue formazan crystals. The media was removed from each well, and the total number of formazan crystals formed was solubilized by adding 100 μL of DMSO. Cell viability was then determined by measuring the absorbance difference between two readings of the same well at 570 nm (MTT) and 690 nm (background) using a Tecan Infinite® 200 PRO microplate reader. The EC₅₀ (half-maximal effective concentration) values were determined as the concentration of the compound that caused 50% inhibition of cell proliferation relative to the untreated control (DMSO in DMEM

or H₂O in DMEM). The data represent the mean of at least three independent experiments (Table S6).

Confocal microscopy studies: Equal numbers (15000 cells/well) of A549 and A375 cells were seeded in μ -Slide 8 Well ibiTreat plates and incubated in a 5% CO₂ incubator at 37 °C for 24 hours before being treated with the compound for 2 hours or 24 hours. The compounds' stock solutions (10 mM) were diluted with DMEM to the desired concentration prior cell treatment. The treatment concentrations were chosen based on the concentration at which no apparent cytotoxic effect was observed in the respective cell lines (Table S7). Afterwards, the cells were washed with PBS (3 x 300 μ L) and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (PAF) for 20 min at room temperature. After removing the fixation solution and washing with PBS (3 x 300 μ L) the cells were treated with a Hoechst solution (2 μ g/mL in PBS) for 10 min at room temperature. The first staining solution was removed, cells washed with PBS (3 x 300 μ L) and treated with CellMask™ Deep Red plasma membrane stain (0.5 μ g/mL) for 10 min at room temperature. After removal of the staining solution and additional washing with PBS (3 x 300 μ L), images were taken with a Stellaris 5, DMI 8 confocal microscope.

Radiolabelling of Pt₂L^{DOTA}₄

All radiolabelling procedures were performed using trace-metal-free reagents and consumables. Lyophilised Pt₂L^{DOTA}₄ cage was dissolved in water to a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

Radiolabelling with gallium-68: The ⁶⁸Ge/⁶⁸Ga-generator was flushed with 5 mL of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid solution. For labelling, 1 mL of the ⁶⁸Ga-eluate (50 MBq) was added to aliquots containing 10, 20, or 50 μ g of the reconstituted Pt₂L^{DOTA}₄ cage, followed by the addition of 1 mL of a 0.25M sodium acetate solution (pH 5.5). The final pH of this mixture was 4.5. This mixture was incubated for 15 min at 95 °C. The crude gallium-68-labelled mixtures were analyzed by ultraviolet-radio-High Performance Liquid Chromatography (UV-radio-HPLC) using a Shimadzu HPLC system equipped with Elysia Raytest acquisition software (GabiNova). An Acclaim 120 C18 column (3 μ m, 120 Å, 4.6 x 150 mm) was used as the stationary phase. A mixture of water, 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (A):acetonitrile, 0.1% TFA (B) was used as eluent with a solvent gradient going from 100% A:0% B to 0% A:100% B in 12.5 minutes at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The injection volume was 50 μ L. The radiochemical purity was determined by manual integration of the peaks detected in the radioactivity channel and the UV channel (254 nm).

Radiolabelling with lutetium-177: The lutetium-177 radiolabelling was performed by adding 5 μ L of ¹⁷⁷LuCl₃ (8.7 MBq; ITM, Germany) to 50 μ g of reconstituted Pt₂L^{DOTA}₄ cage and 1 mL of 0.25M sodium acetate solution (pH 5.5), after which it was heated at 95 °C for 15 minutes. The radiolabelled cage was analysed by ultraviolet-radio-High Performance Liquid Chromatography (UV-radio-HPLC) using a Shimadzu HPLC system equipped with Elysia Raytest acquisition software (GabiNova). An Acclaim 120 C18 column (3 μ m, 120 Å, 4.6 x 150 mm) was used as the stationary phase. A mixture of water, 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (A): MeCN, 0.1% TFA (B) was used as the solvent gradient, going from 100% A:0% B to 0% A:100% B in 12.5 minutes at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The injection volume was 50 μ L. The radiochemical purity was determined by manual integration of the peaks detected in the radioactivity channel and the UV channel (254 nm).

Further details regarding the methods can be found in the Supplemental Methods.

Resource and Availability

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Prof. Angela Casini (angela.casini@tum.de)

Materials Availability

There are restrictions to the availability of metallacage compounds because of the lack of an external centralized repository for their distribution and our need to maintain the stock. We are glad to share metallacages with reasonable compensation by requestor for its processing and shipping.

Data and Code Availability

- Original data of the confocal microscopy studies have been deposited at Zenodo and are publicly available at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18759191.
- This paper does not report original code.
- Any additional information required to reanalyze the data reported in this paper is available from the lead contact upon request.
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Supplemental information

Document S1. Supplemental methods, Figures S1–S38, Scheme S1 and Tables S1–S8.

Data S1 and S2. CIF and checkcif files of the reported XRD structure.

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Authors Contribution

Conceptualization, A.C. and G. M-A. Methodology, A.C., G. M-A. and N.W. Formal Analysis, A.C., G. M-A., N.W., J.Z., A.P. Investigation, N.W., F.B., C.W., L.R. D.B., D.K., J.Z., B. vdW. Data curation: A.C., G. M-A., N.W. and A.P. Resources, A.C., A.P. and A.P. Writing – original draft, N.W, G. M-A. and A.C. Writing – review and editing, all authors. Supervision, G. M-A., A.C., A.P.

Declaration of Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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